

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TOMMY****FIRST NAME: ALLIEU****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
4. Style Guide and the Need to Have One (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expression (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

My dream-come-true journey to the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program in International Public Health started with mixed feelings of anxiety and excitement. I even thought of reading all the materials planned for the course instead of the period when my instructor advised me to go one step after the other.

I have read and watched the training contents related to period one and found it so reach to help me sail smoothly through the ACA-401D course.

I chose academic writing, punctuation, plagiarism, style guide and the need to have one, some rules of thumb for writing, and Latin abbreviations and expressions. These topics have helped me learn new things about academic writing. RP1 took me through grammar and how common mistakes are made, which is really helpful as I start the journey through the PhD program.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY

Generally, an academic essay is a structured form of scholarly explanation or findings that follows steps in writing an essay. It includes the broad parts; introduction, body, and conclusion that aims at providing answers to research questions and hypotheses. They can be in the form of journals, dissertations, literature reviews, relevant research, etc. This type of writing helps authors build and demonstrate knowledge and creativity. It defines questions or arguments as mentioned above to answer questions that will maintain or disprove hypotheses. Academic essays are usually shorter and portray the author's view more than others in an argument.

Ensure a good outcome in academic essay writing will involve early plan and not and not procrastinating to have everything before starting. In-depth knowledge of the research subject is by reading as much as possible literature reviews of past writings related to it, following a universally standardized style and enhancement of clarity (EUCLID 2021, 7-10).

There are four groups of academic writing - expository, narrative, descriptive, and persuasive that serve unique purposes. Expository and persuasive types are most commonly seen in university curriculums as they are more scientific and objective. Narrative and descriptive essays are more subjective and engage your creativity. The four essential questions to answer to start academic writing are the thesis statement, body points/sub-points, a connection, and the summary. Do more finding of materials to read that are accessible and reliable that can broaden ideas on the subject matter. An essay should be balanced and not just look at one side of the coin in key arguments and other essential aspects of the essay topic (EUCLID 2021, 7-10).

3) RULE OF THUMB IN ACADEMIC ESSAY

For academic essay writing to be successful, reviewing the structure as mentioned above will be important, as clarity of points, especially the main one, frequent revision of the document paragraph after the other, chronology of ideas/points, if questions are answered, the argument makes sense and checks if the essay is grammatically ok.

A good essay will include the main thesis (opening paragraph), staying focused on relevant points and the topic when critically assessing the paper, avoiding sweeping statements, clarity again is very important, etc. Starting most sentences with a subject will reduce readers' appetite for the paper. Even though it is not good to have a lot of quotations, remember to support assertions made by those whose papers you extract information from and take those views with utmost importance.

4) PUNCTUATION

Punctuation marks are simply put as created symbol to create and support meaning within a sentence or to break it up. There are 14 common punctuation marks in use in English grammar. They are the period, question mark, exclamation point, comma, semicolon, colon, dash, hyphen, parentheses, brackets, braces, apostrophe, quotation marks, and ellipsis (EUCLID 2021, 16-23).

An apostrophe is used to show that certain letters have been omitted from a word (contractions, ie, she's, it's...). The apostrophe symbols are used to show the possessive form of a noun (possessive apostrophe), in addition to indicating the plural form of lowercase letters.

Brackets are squared/rounded/angled-off quotations ([]) that are used to show information of a technical nature. Even if this information is omitted entirely, the sentence would still make sense.

Bullets and numbers are used with listings, examples or to shorten a complex description. They are also good for added support with details, designating steps in a process, giving a list of parts or ingredients, and defining terms.

A colon (:) is varied in uses. It is used to introduce a quotation, a series, or even an explanation. It is also used to separate two independent clauses.

A semicolon (;) is used to separate two independent clauses while still demonstrating that a close relationship exists between them. The semicolon does a better job of showing the connection between two statements than a full stop would.

To better understand the use of the comma, the following eight basic uses are to separate independent clauses, after the introductory clause or phrase, between all items in a series, to set off non-restrictive clauses, to set off appositives, to indicate direct address, to set off direct quotations, dates, addresses, titles, and numbers.

While dashes connect all types of words, hyphens link words that are compound. The various types are m-dash (—), which can replace commas, n-dash (–), and although less used, it can be used to write dates and time, scores, in connections and conflicts, and compound adjectives.

A full stop is chiefly used at the end of a full sentence or a statement considered complete. It is also used after a title as a decimal and abbreviation.

We use exclamations (!) to show excitement or emphasis.

Questions should always be finished with a question mark (!) as well as in a sentence posing uncertainty.

When writing a complete statement within quotation marks, we only use a period at the end of the complete sentence. They are used to capture spoken words, titles of longer works, single quotes, rare quotes,

A slash (/), which is also known as a forward slash, a virgule, or even an oblique dash, is used to separate lines in songs, poems, etc (EUCLID 2021, 44-53).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is an academic denies the author acknowledgment of his/her work. It is an offense that must be avoided at all times by doing proper citation, quotation, paraphrasing, statistic/data, visuals etc, if needed so that there is an acknowledgment of someone's work. It is not only unfair but unethical to use someone's work without correct acknowledgment. It is good not to cite information that does not add value to the essay eg, common knowledge, an idea that has multiple information sources (EUCLID 2021, 34-39).

While using someone else's work (including, in particular, scientific publications) without the affiliation of authorship is an infringement of copyright moral rights, from a legal point of view, self-plagiarism is a neutral practice. The duplication of one's work or a significant part of it without a proper and clear reference to an earlier publication may be, however, considered an infringement of the principles of reliability and ethics in science. It may also have negative consequences for procedures for obtaining scientific degrees and titles. It also exposes the author of the self-plagiarism to a loss of scientific credibility and reputation (Ożegalska-Trybalska 2021).

6) STYLE GUIDE AND NEED

Since the style guide represents the writer's approach to documentation, carrying it out needs very good consistency, coherence, and standard in materials. Style guides are usually restricted to some types of skilled writing. The guideline ensures that the finished work does not reflect the author's personal style but the standard style based on the guides. The challenge in the style guide is the lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English which means that there is always a certain amount of debate on elements of style (EUCLID 2021, 41-44).

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Latin abbreviations and expressions are used for many reasons. In writing, they are used in footnotes, bibliographies, businesses, information in parentheses, flyers, and press.

Latin abbreviations are very helpful in scientific writing, such as health (EUCLID 2021, 58-64).

Common Latin abbreviations are: acc. = acceptum = received, abamic. = ab amico = from a friend, abinit. = ab inito = at first, *absque.* = *absque* = without, *a.c.* = *anni currentis* = this year, *acq., acqu.* = *acquisitum, acquisitio* = purchased, *a d.* = *a dato* = from the date of (signature), *adnot.* = *adnotavit* = a mark, marked, *ad fin.* = *ad finem* = to the end, *adint* = *ad interim* = previously, *ad. lib.* = *ad libitum* = optional and *a. f.* = *anni futuri* = next year

8) CONCLUSION

This part of the course met my expectations, and I must confess that it is helpful to the commencement of my study. It is essential that every PhD program starts with ACA-401D, and the choice of having it as the first is not a mistake at all.

In academic essay writing, it was clear that plagiarism is unacceptable and an infringement of the principles of reliability and ethics must be avoided. Rules around not overusing punctuation marks were also awesome. It helped me learnt that successful academic writing requires a strong command of the rhetorical moves that orient the reader to the theme and substantive material of an academic essay.

My conclusion is that the ACA-401D course is rich and deserves its position of being the first encounter for the doctoral program. I see challenges in navigating through the program, but I am ready to face them confidently to succeed.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University

Cleenewerck, Laurent, Director. 2021. *ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo video.

Ożegalska-Trybalska, Justyna. 2021. "Plagiarism and Self-Plagiarism – Facts and Myths." *Nowotwory* 71 (1). *Via Medica*: 70–72. doi:10.5603/NJO.2021.0012.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.